

Email: [REDACTED]
Telephone: +1 (857) [REDACTED]

MEMORANDUM

DATE: September 29th, 2021

FROM: [REDACTED]

TO: The Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal, and Parliamentary Affairs

SUBJECT: OPPOSITION TO THE PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL, 2021

SUMMARY

The following is a Memorandum in Opposition to the passage of the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill ("The Bill"). My reasons for opposition are as follows:

1. The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill contravenes the principles of non-discrimination and freedom of speech and association outlined in the Constitution of Ghana.
2. The Bill violates Articles 2 and 3 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, to which Ghana is a signatory.
3. The Bill jeopardizes Ghana's status as a champion of democracy and human rights, by promoting the violation of international human rights standards.

ANALYSIS

- 1. The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill contravenes the principles of non-discrimination and freedom of speech and association outlined in the Ghana Constitution.**

The Ghana Constitution demonstrates a clear commitment to protect and support vulnerable populations, particularly in Chapter 5: Fundamental Human Rights and Freedoms.

Chapter 5, Section 15 states that *"the dignity of all persons shall be inviolable."*

Chapter 5, Section 21 states that every Ghanaian citizen has the right to *"freedom of speech and expression, which shall include freedom of the press and other media; freedom of thought, conscience and belief, which shall include academic freedom; freedom of assembly including freedom to take part in processions and demonstrations; and freedom of association, which shall include freedom to form or join trade unions or other associations, national and international, for the protection of their interest."*¹

By promoting legislation that outlaws human rights advocacy, media expression, and the formation of civil society groups to protect vulnerable populations from gender and orientation-based discrimination, the Parliament of Ghana is directly contravening the constitutionally-guaranteed freedoms outlined above.

¹ https://www.constituteproject.org/constitution/Ghana_1996.pdf

2. The Bill violates Articles 2 and 3 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, to which Ghana is a signatory as of July 2004.

Article 2 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights states: *"Every individual shall be entitled to the enjoyment of the rights and freedoms recognized and guaranteed in the present Charter **without distinction of any kind** such as race, ethnic group, colour, sex, language, religion, political or any other opinion, national and social origin, fortune, birth **or other status**."*²

A person's gender or sexual orientation should fall under the "other status" listed above. By enacting discriminatory and punitive legislation that directly harms individuals based on their gender identity or sexual orientation, the Parliament of Ghana would be violating the principles of this Charter, to which Ghana is a signatory as of July 2004.

3. The Bill jeopardizes Ghana's status as a champion of democracy and human rights, by promoting the violation of international human rights standards.

Ghana is a signatory to numerous human rights instruments that aim to protect and uplift historically marginalized people, including but not limited to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (ratified in 1986), the Convention on the Rights of the Child (ratified in 1990), and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ratified in 2000).³ Ghana has committed to upholding the principles of nondiscrimination and protection outlined in these conventions, and the passage of the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill would damage the country's reputation as a champion of human rights.

The international community has expressed grave concerns regarding the proposed Bill. Representatives of the United Nations Human Rights Council have stated that *"The proposed law promotes deeply harmful practices that amount to ill-treatment and are conducive to torture,"* and that *"if it were to be adopted, this legislation could create a recipe for conflict and violence."*⁴ Ghana could face serious reputational harm and global backlash, including economic consequences and damaged relationships with diplomatic partners, by pursuing such patently discriminatory legislation against a vulnerable subgroup of the population.

CONCLUSION

Due to the reasons stated above, I am opposed to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill. I believe that it is the responsibility of the Parliament of Ghana to conceptualize and pass legislation that protects every person's ability to reach their full human potential, and guarantees equal treatment, respect, and opportunity for all. Therefore, I respectfully call upon Parliament not to pass the Bill.

Thank you for your consideration,

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Consultant

² https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36390-treaty-0011_-_african_charter_on_human_and_peoples_rights_e.pdf

³ <http://www.standghana.org/your-rights/human-rights-instruments-ghana-ratified/>

⁴ <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/NewsEvents/Pages/DisplayNews.aspx?NewsID=27378&LangID=E>